

Rethinking Networked Robotics in the 6G Era with Generative AI-in-the-Loop

Peizheng Li, Xinyi Lin, Adnan Aijaz

Abstract—Networked robotics continues to be a key component of various industrial systems. 6G will empower networked robotics with the envisaged capabilities like hyper-reliable and low-latency connectivity and in-network intelligence. While communication and control techniques have been widely investigated; co-design and AI-based solutions for autonomy and reasoning are still emerging. In this article, we propose a generative AI-in-the-Loop (GITL) framework for the control and coordination of networked robotic systems. The generative AI (GAI) agent oversees three interrelated loops: the communication loop, the robot control loop, and the AI model control loop, making holistic decisions by interpreting task requirements, network status, and robotic operations. Acting as a high-level cross-domain coordinator, the GAI agent leverages background knowledge of AI models, robot behaviors, and network policies, ensuring seamless interplay across different operational scenarios. This approach ultimately enables a highly autonomous networked robotic system capable of handling complex tasks with minimal human intervention. We anticipate that the GITL paradigm will play a pivotal role in unlocking the full potential of networked robotic systems, enabling enhanced autonomy, adaptability, and coordination in the emerging 6G and Industry 5.0 era.

Index Terms—6G, AI-native, generative AI-in-the-loop, generative agent, networked robotics, control loops, SemCom.

I. INTRODUCTION

With the rapid advancement of control and communication technologies, the robotics industry is transforming. Robots are increasingly deployed in dynamic and unstructured environments for tasks such as transportation, inspection, and assembly. To support these operations, networks must provide reliable, low-latency connectivity for real-time data exchange and control. artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) techniques, including federated learning (FL), reinforcement learning (RL), and edge intelligence, are now progressively integrated into both network and robotic platforms. Rising task complexity and customization needs are driving demand for AI-powered robotics, including humanoid, swarm, and assembly robots that enable smart, autonomous manufacturing.

To achieve seamless system-level operation and coordination, three critical requirements must be met from both the communication and robotics perspectives: (a) reliable and deterministic communication, (b) automation of robotic tasks, and (c) real-time data collection, processing, and responsive decision-making [1]. In this context, a plethora of research has highlighted the significant role of communication–control

co-design in unlocking the full potential of networked robotic systems.

However, challenges persist in real-world deployments due to several factors: (a) the communication network that provides connectivity is often designed and operated in a rigid and static manner, making it difficult to adapt to dynamic robotic environments with specific latency and throughput requirements; (b) robotic systems are typically developed and operated in isolation, limiting their ability to adjust to changing network conditions or task demands; and (c) fragmented standardization efforts between the communication and robotics communities have led to gaps in interoperability standards, hindering the seamless integration required for network-driven robotic services [2].

Recent advances in communication and generative AI (GAI) have opened new opportunities for the joint design of robot control and communication. Semantic communication (SemCom) introduces a novel paradigm that reduces communication overhead by transmitting only the most relevant information necessary for collaborative task execution among robots. Meanwhile, the advent of open radio access network (Open RAN) offers a more flexible and programmable network architecture through its disaggregated design and the integration of intelligent xApps and rApps, enabling near-real-time, fine-grained control and management of network resources. In parallel, GAI models, such as large language models (LLMs), have demonstrated remarkable capabilities in understanding, reasoning, and content generation, which hold great promise for enhancing robotic decision-making and control strategies. According to *market.us*¹, GAI in robotics is expected to be a 23B USD global market by 2033, growing at a CAGR of 35% from 2024.

The seamless integration and interaction of these emerging technologies offer potential to transform the design and operation of networked robotic systems in the 6G era. The standardization landscape for 6G-enabled robotic services has been comprehensively reviewed in [3], highlighting key technical and regulatory developments. Concurrently, recent progress has demonstrated the effectiveness of GAI in facilitating coordination and task allocation within robotic swarms. Notably, frameworks such as LLM-based hierarchical planners and hybrid architectures have been proposed in [4], offering promising directions for scalable and adaptive multi-robot collaboration. [5] presents a swarm robot-based fully automated production system leveraging LLMs.

The authors are with the Bristol Research and Innovation Laboratory, Toshiba Europe Ltd., U.K. (e-mail: peizheng.li@toshiba-bril.com).

This work was supported by the 6G-GOALS project under the 6G SNS-JU Horizon program, n.101139232.

¹<https://market.us/report/generative-ai-in-robotics-market/>

However, most existing studies treat the GAI/LLM merely as an external controller for robotic operations, overlooking a holistic system-level perspective. 6G features such as in-network AI and integrated sensing will further expand industrial applications. As depicted in Fig. 1, these applications can be grouped into three broad categories: intelligent production and operations, ubiquitous connectivity and flexible manufacturing, and secure sensing and human-in-the-loop integration. Undoubtedly, the functional and connectivity enhancements offered by 6G can further strengthen robotic systems in these emerging scenarios.

In this paper, we introduce the concept of generative AI-in-the-loop (GITL) for networked robotics, aiming to enable task-oriented and autonomous operations². The GITL framework constitutes a high-level yet comprehensive control loop that leverages generative AI as reasoning and decision-making agents. Its core function is to continuously monitor and adapt the execution policies across three interconnected dimensions: (a) dynamic adaptation of network resources to support robotic operations; (b) real-time adjustment of robotic behaviors to meet evolving task requirements; (c) continual refinement of AI models based on feedback from robotic and network performance. By interpreting task goals, network conditions, and robotic actions, GITL enables intelligent decision-making to optimize overall system performance [7].

The novelty of the proposed GITL framework lies in the integration of GAI as a multi-level controller across key system loops, thereby assigning it a more functional and central role within the networked robotics architecture. Specifically, GITL enables the following capabilities:

- **GAI in the communication loop:** GAI supports connectivity-centric control and orchestration, encompassing bandwidth allocation, resource scheduling, and network slicing. This aligns with emerging practices such as intent-based networking, end-to-end resource management, network slicing, and SemCom.
- **GAI in the robot control loop:** GAI facilitates task-centric planning and coordination at the robotic level, including task decomposition, allocation, and execution across multiple robotic agents, enabling more adaptive and efficient task management.
- **GAI in the AI model control loop:** GAI also oversees the performance monitoring, updating, and lifecycle management of embedded AI models, ensuring continuous learning and adaptation in dynamic environments.

By embedding shared domain knowledge of the robotic system, network configuration, and AI models, GAI serves as a unifying agent capable of harmonizing these subsystems for diverse operational scenarios. The GITL framework aspires to realize a fully autonomous networked robotic system capable of executing complex tasks with minimal human intervention.

II. BACKGROUND AND MOTIVATION

The properties of the networked robot node, such as the ease of programming, operation, and maintenance, make it suitable

²A related but distinct discussion on GAI-in-the-loop for next-generation networks can be found in [6].

Fig. 1. Scenarios of the 6G for industrial applications (the industrial scene used as the background was partially generated by ChatGPT).

for a wide range of industrial applications, including mission-critical scenarios, unstructured environments, and tasks subject to continuous change. Fundamentally, the successful operation of a multi-robot system depends on three interrelated elements: communication, control, and task allocation [8]. Robots with centralised/hybrid control via 6G network are attractive, as they provide real-time communication and control.

A. Semantic-aware connectivity

Semantic-aware connectivity stems from the SemCom, which leverages the SemCom principles, including the semantic compression and goal-oriented communication, in the networked-robot operation, to reduce the communication overhead and improve the efficiency of the multi-robot system. With semantic-aware connectivity, only the information relevant to achieving a specific goal or task is transmitted.

However, in practice, semantic models must dynamically adapt their encoder–decoder design, joint source channel coding (JSCC) scheme, and compression rate to environmental conditions. SemCom also requires network-side orchestration to meet quality of service (QoS) from the UE.

B. AI-native networks and MLOps

AI/ML has become central to network optimization, forming the core of AI-native networking research. The AI/ML models are used to replace the classical communication function blocks and stacks for cross-layer and more global optimization of the radio resources. AI and network, programmability and open architecture are crucial in this process. Meanwhile, in the advanced Open RAN architecture, the extra AI/ML applications can be deployed in the network for different

TABLE I
COMPARISON OF SWARM, CENTRALIZED, AND GAI-IN-THE-LOOP CONTROL METHODS

Aspect	Swarm Control [9], [10], [11]	Centralized Control [12], [13], [14]	GAI-in-the-loop Control
Response Speed	<i>Strength:</i> Enables distributed, local decision-making with minimal latency in small teams. <i>Weakness:</i> Response may degrade with number of agents; emergent behavior can be slow to converge.	<i>Strength:</i> Coordinated global scheduling enables highly optimized, real-time responses. <i>Weakness:</i> May introduce bottlenecks under scale.	<i>Strength:</i> Allows semantic-level, fast inference with real-time adaptation to task and context. <i>Weakness:</i> Inference latency varies with model size and hardware support.
Adaptivity	<i>Strength:</i> Rapid adaptation to local environment changes without central dependency. <i>Weakness:</i> Lacks global context awareness, may fail in coordinate replanning.	<i>Strength:</i> Global state awareness supports planned adaptation. <i>Weakness:</i> Requires complete replanning, not suitable for dynamic tasks.	<i>Strength:</i> Learns and adapts over time; can tune robot/network/policy jointly. <i>Weakness:</i> Requires retraining or fine-tuning, which can be resource-intensive.
Accuracy	<i>Strength:</i> Quick response to local needs. <i>Weakness:</i> Global optimality is often compromised due to partial observability.	<i>Strength:</i> Can achieve high accuracy through centralized optimization. <i>Weakness:</i> Sensitive to sensor noise and modeling errors.	<i>Strength:</i> Balances between accuracy and generalization; learns patterns from diverse data. <i>Weakness:</i> Depends heavily on training data quality and coverage.
Scalability	<i>Strength:</i> Naturally scalable; no single point of control. <i>Weakness:</i> Difficult to maintain coordination in large swarms.	<i>Strength:</i> Efficient for small-to-medium systems. <i>Weakness:</i> Scalability constrained by central computation and communication load.	<i>Strength:</i> GAI improves generalization across team sizes; can be offload controlled. <i>Weakness:</i> May require model retraining for large changes.
Communication Overhead	<i>Strength:</i> Minimal communication. <i>Weakness:</i> Lacks coordinated behavior without communication.	<i>Strength:</i> Full control via high-bandwidth communication. <i>Weakness:</i> High communication overhead and potential for congestion.	<i>Strength:</i> Can reduce communication with embedded intelligence. <i>Weakness:</i> Architecture-dependent; AI modeling can be complex.
Cost	<i>Strength:</i> Low per-agent cost; lightweight hardware. <i>Weakness:</i> Complex behavior needs careful design.	<i>Strength:</i> Cost-effective when accuracy is prioritized. <i>Weakness:</i> High infrastructure and computing cost.	<i>Strength:</i> Reusable across tasks; inference cost is moderate. <i>Weakness:</i> Expensive training and (G)AI pipeline setup.
Fault Tolerance	<i>Strength:</i> High fault tolerance; system degrades gracefully. <i>Weakness:</i> Hard to debug and control failure propagation.	<i>Strength:</i> Central authority simplifies fault detection. <i>Weakness:</i> Vulnerable to central failure.	<i>Strength:</i> GAI can be distributed or cloud-based; improves redundancy. <i>Weakness:</i> Performance may degrade if GAI is unavailable or inconsistent.
Design Complexity	<i>Strength:</i> Simple agent logic can lead to complex emergent behavior. <i>Weakness:</i> Hard to predict and control emergent outcomes.	<i>Strength:</i> Central planning allows holistic design. <i>Weakness:</i> High system complexity.	<i>Strength:</i> Automates control decisions, simplifies runtime logic. <i>Weakness:</i> Requires ML expertise to design and maintain.

purposes, such as network slicing, resource allocation, and network management.

These xApps/rApps can be used to optimize the network for robot operation. In this case, network-aware task decomposition and intelligent allocation mechanisms distribute workloads based on real-time network and robot conditions, enhancing operational effectiveness.

Deployed AI/ML models often generalize poorly to unseen scenarios. Therefore, for these deployed AI/ML models, a lifecycle management process is necessary to monitor and update the models for the changing network and robot operation environment. This process is usually termed ML operations (MLOps). In MLOps, the engineers have to define the criteria for AI/ML updates, and for multiple models, different lifecycle management strategies are needed [15]. Inevitably, MLOps is a time-consuming and experience-driven process, which is not suitable for the dynamic and complex networked robot system.

C. Robot control

From the perspective of robot control, the evolution of networked robotics demands a shift from traditional control-centric methods to more integrated and adaptive solutions. The representative examples of robotics systems include collaborative robots (cobots), such as automated guided vehicles (AGVs) and autonomous mobile robots (AMRs). These cobots leverage sophisticated sensor systems, such as force sensing, vision, and proximity detection, combined with reliable communication links, enabling autonomous navigation, obstacle avoidance, and real-time collaboration with both humans and other robots.

Traditional cobot operations have predominantly relied on predefined rules and static environmental assumptions, leading to limited adaptability in dynamically changing or uncertain operating conditions. To address these limitations, recent research has advocated for a communication-control co-design paradigm, emphasizing real-time data exchange and dynamic coordination among robots. This approach improves flexibility and task-allocation efficiency.

Fig. 2. GITL architecture for networked robotics in 6G, wherein the light green box in the center indicates the part involving the AI model within both the Open RAN and robot systems.

However, practical deployment challenges persist, notably concerning communication overhead, synchronization complexity, and efficient task allocation. The intensive information exchange required in multi-robot operations can result in network congestion, latency issues, and excessive energy consumption, potentially compromising operational effectiveness.

Addressing these challenges necessitates a paradigm shift toward intelligent, adaptive control strategies facilitated by AI. On one hand, the AI models for realizing the semantic-awareness connectivity are able to significantly reduce communication overhead, transmitting only essential information relevant to task completion and collective coordination. On the other hand, the promising GAI-driven methods enable understanding and reasoning of task requirements, robot states, and environmental conditions, facilitating more intelligent decision-making and adaptive coordination.

Ultimately, for the connectivity and control-centric robot control, the GITL method helps to build an autonomous, semantic-level, and intent-aware control agent. This closed-loop control system utilizes feedback from robot operations, communication status and network operation to continuously refine control strategies, ensuring optimized performance in dynamic environments.

To better contextualize the benefits and limitations of GITL, we present a comparative analysis of three mainstream robotic control strategies, swarm control, centralized control, and the proposed GAI-in-the-loop control, across multiple dimensions in Table I.

As shown in Table I, GITL combines the strengths of swarm and centralized control—retaining adaptability and scalability while enabling goal-aware coordination.

III. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE OF GITL

A. System architecture overview

Fig. 2 illustrates the proposed GITL framework for the autonomous networked robotics in the 6G era. The core of the architecture is the GAI agent, which acts as a high-level reasoning and decision-making entity that supervises and coordinates three critical system loops:

- GAI for the Communication Loop:** The GAI agent generates connectivity-centric commands to optimize network resources such as bandwidth, latency, and slicing via the Open RAN architecture. This loop continuously adapts communication strategies based on communication performance feedback received from the networked robotics system and the Open RAN infrastructure. The Open RAN relies on both near-real-time and non-real-time RAN intelligent controllers (RICs), and the deployed AI models to support fine-grained, intelligent network control. Although GITL is architecture-agnostic, Open RAN is used here for its programmability and maturity in AI-driven control.
- GAI for the Robot Control Loop:** In this loop, the GAI agent issues task-centric commands to orchestrate robot behavior. This includes task decomposition, allocation, and coordination among robot nodes. The loop operates based on robot environment feedback, which reflects the current task progress, environmental changes, and operational status of the robots. This ensures responsive, dynamic control of robots operating in complex, real-world environments.
- GAI for the AI Model Control Loop:** The GAI agent also monitors and manages the performance of embedded

AI models within both the robots and the network infrastructure. By analyzing AI model performance feedback, it provides AI model-centric commands to fine-tune or re-train models using the principles of MLOps. This ensures the continual improvement and contextual adaptation of AI models in real time.

While the architecture distinguishes the communication loop, robot control loop, and AI model control loop as separate functional pathways, it is crucial to recognize that these loops do not operate in isolation. Instead, they form a tightly coupled, co-dependent control system, with the GAI agent acting as the orchestrator to ensure cross-loop coordination.

The deployment of the GAI agent can adopt either a distributed or cloud-based architecture, depending on the latency tolerance, computational capacity, and energy efficiency requirements of the networked robotic system. In distributed deployments, edge or on-device agents enable faster response times and improved fault tolerance but raise challenges related to synchronization, state consistency, and communication overhead among distributed nodes. Conversely, centralized or cloud-based deployments offer greater computational power and global situational awareness, yet may suffer from longer control loops and increased dependency on reliable, high-bandwidth connectivity. These trade-offs must be carefully considered and balanced to ensure that the GITL framework meets the real-time, reliability, and scalability demands of diverse 6G robotic applications.

The communication loop adaptively manages latency, reliability, and bandwidth for robotic operations and AI model updates. In turn, the robot control loop depends on timely and context-aware communication to ensure accurate task allocation and coordination among distributed robotic agents. The effectiveness of both loops is further enhanced by the AI model control loop, which ensures that the underlying AI models guiding robot behavior and network decisions are contextually relevant and continuously updated.

By leveraging shared knowledge and real-time feedback signals, including communication performance, robot environment feedback, and AI model performance, the GAI agent coordinates the three loops in a holistic and goal-driven manner. This cross-loop synergy enables the system to make informed, adaptive decisions that optimize task execution, resource utilization, and overall system efficiency.

While the integration of GAI enhances system intelligence, it also introduces additional computational complexity and energy consumption. To mitigate these challenges, the GITL framework can employ model compression and optimization techniques (e.g., pruning, quantization, knowledge distillation) and adopt adaptive inference policies that dynamically balance performance with energy efficiency. Moreover, leveraging semantic compression and edge-cloud cooperation can further reduce communication overhead and promote sustainable operation across the three loops.

B. GAI for communication loops

GAI, particularly LLMs, in communication systems has emerged as a prominent research area, driven by the models'

powerful semantic understanding and reasoning capabilities. This paradigm can be analyzed from two complementary perspectives.

At the network level, LLMs act as intent-based controllers translating high-level goals into network configurations. At the connectivity level, GAI supports semantic encoding/decoding and hyperparameter selection (e.g., compression ratio, JSCC scheme) according to channel and QoS conditions.

These two aspects can significantly contribute to the networked robot operation. For instance, when the service priority, latency, and bandwidth consumption information, etc., are passed to the centralised network via this GAI communication loop, network resources and semantic model configurations can be rearranged to satisfy the new requirements of the vertical robot scenarios. This can be operated in a (near) real-time way as long as the robot's operational requirements and environmental feedback can be provided promptly. The GAI for communication loops can establish the end-to-end optimization for robot-centric connectivity and generate the reliability policies to suit changing robotic operations in complex, dynamic environments via protective adaptation of the communication layer.

C. GAI for robot control loops

The integration of GAI/LLMs into robot control loops offers a transformative approach for bridging the gap between high-level reasoning and real-world robotic tasks. As outlined in [4], GAI-based systems can operate at four distinct instruction levels: high-level task allocation, mid-level motion planning, low-level action generation, and human intervention. For example, at the high-level allocation stage, LLMs can decompose a complex task into smaller subtasks suited to each robot node's capabilities, while at the mid-level, LLM-based planners leverage semantic understanding of the environment to coordinate motion paths and obstacle avoidance.

In multi-agent settings, GAI enhances collaboration by enabling robots to share and interpret complex instructions more clearly. Furthermore, LLMs are often combined with advanced ML techniques, such as RL and Graph NN, to improve both efficiency and precision in robot control and action generation.

Embedding GAI within the robot control loop not only optimizes immediate task execution but also supports continuous learning and adaptation. By aggregating and analyzing real-time feedback on environmental conditions and operational performance, the GAI agent can constantly refine task decomposition, scheduling strategies, and collaboration mechanisms.

D. GAI for AI model lifecycle loops

An often-overlooked yet critical element of autonomous networked systems is the lifecycle management of their AI models. In this context, GAI/LLMs can substantially streamline the development, deployment, monitoring, and continual enhancement of models deployed at the edge, in the RIC, or within the core network. By interpreting performance drift, system requirements, and operational feedback, GAI agents can recommend/automate model updates and hyperparameter

Fig. 3. The interaction and working process of three loops.

tuning strategies. This resonates strongly with the MLOps paradigm, transforming model maintenance from a static event into an ongoing process.

Moreover, GAI agents detect concept drift or performance degradation by comparing observed outcomes with expected behaviours in real time. When deviations emerge—due to environmental changes or evolving robot tasks—GAI-driven solutions can rapidly initiate targeted model retraining using curated data, or orchestrate pipelines in containerized, continuous-integration environments. This closed loop keeps models accurate and reliable, strengthening 6G robotic autonomy.

E. The GAI-agent operational sequence among three loops

In a networked robotic system, the GAI-agent lies at the heart of three major loops: the communication loop, the robot control loop, and the AI model lifecycle loop. These loops are triggered by various events, such as communication bottlenecks, changes in robot tasks, or AI model performance shifts. For instance, the service management and orchestration (SMO) layer might detect a network issue like increased latency or low throughput, prompting the GAI-agent to adjust resources in the communication loop. Likewise, if a robot faces a new task requirement or encounters unexpected obstacles, it triggers the robot control loop to request dynamic task decomposition and scheduling strategies from the GAI-agent. Meanwhile, AI model lifecycle concerns surface whenever the system detects signs of performance drift or concept drift, resulting in a prompt to the GAI-agent for retraining or reconfiguring the relevant models. The interaction and working process of these three loops are illustrated in Fig. 3.

Once these triggers occur, the GAI-agent constructs an appropriate prompt that encapsulates the current constraints and objectives. In the communication loop, this may include bandwidth requirements, QoS targets, and slicing policies; for the robot control loop, the prompt typically contains real-time feedback about task priorities, robot availability, and environmental changes; and for the AI model lifecycle loop, the prompt highlights shifts in model accuracy, data distribution anomalies, or newly encountered contexts. The GAI-agent processes these prompts in a logical order, reconciling competing demands across network resources, robot tasks, and model maintenance needs. The agent then generates an actionable plan (spanning multi-step commands), before passing it to the respective loop for execution.

Finally, each loop feeds real-time feedback back into the GAI-agent, creating a closed loop of continuous adaptation. Whenever the assigned plan is partially executed or new system feedback arises, like an abrupt surge in network load, changes in robot dynamics, or further model degradation, the GAI-agent refines its prompts and updates the instructions accordingly. This iterative process ensures that the three loops function harmoniously.

Beyond functional efficiency, the deployment of GAI within the GITL architecture also raises ethical and safety considerations. Ensuring accountability, transparency, and explainability is essential to prevent unintended outcomes during autonomous operations. Integrating human-in-the-loop supervision, decision traceability, and robust auditing mechanisms can enhance system trustworthiness. Moreover, incorporating safety constraints within the GAI agent's policy generation process helps maintain operational integrity and supports responsible AI deployment in 6G-enabled robotic environments.

Fig. 4. GITL for networked robotics decision-making process.

IV. DEPLOYMENT SCENARIOS AND A CASE STUDY

A. Deployment scenarios

The preceding sections outlined the core concepts and operations of the GITL framework for networked robot control. This section briefly discusses its potential deployment scenarios. A key evolution in 6G is the shift toward open, disaggregated, and intelligent network architectures that can serve as centralized controllers for diverse vertical applications. Embedding the GAI agent within 6G infrastructure—such as the RAN—is particularly promising, as internal interfaces can efficiently collect in-network data to support connectivity management and AI model lifecycle control.

In terms of scalability, the GITL framework can evolve from small-scale testbeds to large industrial deployments by leveraging distributed edge nodes and cloud coordination. This enables gradual integration and validation in physical environments while preserving real-time performance.

However, exchanging observations and data between individual robot nodes and a centralized RAN remains challenging. In practice, these interactions can be routed through an application server in the core network or via a multi-access edge computing (MEC) platform associated with the RAN. Both approaches require tight coordination across protocols, scheduling, and applications to ensure low-latency reliability.

B. A case study

We consider an indoor industrial-surveillance case where multiple robots monitor and detect device anomalies. A GAI agent is embedded in the workflow to support decision-making across three core aspects of the GITL architecture:

- **Connectivity Optimization based on GAI:** The GAI-agent determines how to establish communication between each robot node and the centralized RAN controller by leveraging NN-based semantic compression. This ensures that only semantically relevant information is transmitted, thereby reducing communication overhead. Each robot sends its local observations to a central server for further assessment of device operating conditions.

- **Robot Routing Strategy:** Based on the real-time understanding of the indoor environment layout, including obstacles, the number of robots and the target devices, the GAI-agent implements an efficient and autonomous routing algorithm to optimize coverage and task distribution.
- **AI Model Lifecycle Management:** An NN classifier running on the central application (at the RAN side) is responsible for determining whether each monitored device is operating normally or abnormally. The model’s classification accuracy and performance metrics are regularly evaluated and sent to the GAI-agent. If performance degradation or a domain mismatch is detected, the GAI-agent can trigger model updates or initiate retraining procedures.

This case study is conducted in a simulated virtual environment, where robot behavior, sensor logs, and environmental interactions are fed into the GAI-agent in real time. The full GITL decision-making process is illustrated in Fig. 4. The GAI-agent is initially provided with system-specific prompts, including the task description, prior examples, and operational constraints, as contextual grounding for prompt interpretation and action generation. Through several rounds of reasoning and response, the GAI-agent is able to recommend the optimal number of robots, a goal-oriented search and patrol strategy, a communication-efficient data transmission scheme, and whether the central classification model requires updating to maintain reliable anomaly detection performance.

The simulation results are presented in Fig. 5, where Fig. 5a illustrates the initial positions of all robots and devices, and Fig. 5b shows the final state after all devices have been inspected. When an abnormal device is detected, its marker changes from a red rhombus to a red cross. Similarly, a normal device changes from a green dot to a blue triangle upon detection. The dashed circles surrounding each robot indicate their respective fields of view. Fig. 5c displays the total data volume transmitted during the monitoring process, comparing scenarios with and without semantic compression of raw data, across different numbers of robots³.

It can be observed from Fig. 5(c) that the total transmitted data increases with the number of robots, while the use of semantic compression significantly reduces this growth. By transmitting only task-relevant information, the SemCom model achieves substantial bandwidth savings, improving scalability and responsiveness in multi-robot coordination. However, this efficiency introduces a trade-off: aggressive compression may slightly reduce the fidelity of the encoded information, which could affect downstream perception and trajectory planning accuracy. In the present setup, this impact remains negligible, as the compression rate is optimized to preserve critical semantic content while minimizing communication overhead.

Further details about the simulation setup, semantic model configuration, and the statistical methods used for measuring transmitted data volume can be found in [1].

³A systematic benchmarking framework for GITL remains a key direction for future work, with potential metrics including communication efficiency, control performance, AI adaptability, and system-level KPIs capturing overall efficiency and scalability.

Fig. 5. Illustration of simulation environment of robot surveillance. (a) shows the initialised environment and robot/device location when the simulation starts. (b) shows the robot’s trajectory when the simulation ends. (c) shows the transmitted data comparison with/without semantic compression.

V. CHALLENGES AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

A. Real-Time inference and latency

A key challenge for GITL lies in balancing real-time responsiveness with robust AI-driven decision-making. Generative models are computationally demanding and may produce inaccurate or inconsistent outputs. In latency-sensitive robotic applications—such as mission-critical inspection and autonomous navigation—ensuring timely and reliable inference is essential. Future research should focus on model compression and edge-distributed inference to further reduce latency.

Another important challenge concerns the adaptability and safety of GAI systems operating in dynamic networked environments. Rapid environmental or task changes require the GAI agent to update or fine-tune its policies with minimal delay and without compromising reliability. Promising directions include lightweight adaptation mechanisms (e.g., few-shot or continual learning) and efficient inference techniques such as speculative decoding. Safety assurance should also be embedded through formal verification and runtime monitoring to maintain dependable operation while preserving real-time responsiveness.

B. Standardization for GAI/6G integration

Although there is substantial research on GAI for communications and vertical applications like robotics, standards and interoperability remain nascent. The diverse ecosystem of vendors may struggle to integrate without common standards and protocols. Future directions in 6G standardization can focus on: (i) defining open interfaces for data exchange among GAI agents, robot nodes, and network controllers; (ii) establishing performance benchmarks to assess GAI-driven control loops under varying network conditions.

C. Knowledge sharing and human-agent collaboration

Effective GITL relies on robust knowledge exchange. Scalable GITL design requires distributed knowledge bases that

synchronize local and global data and lightweight agents coordinating communication, control, and model management. On the other hand, while the ultimate goal of this paper is to enable autonomous networked robotics through GITL, human expertise remains essential. Future work should design intuitive interfaces and safe intervention modes for effective human–agent collaboration.

D. Trustworthiness and security

As GAI becomes integral to robot operations, security threats such as data poisoning, adversarial attacks, or malicious instruction prompts become increasingly critical. Moreover, privacy concerns arise when personal or sensitive data is processed by GAI models. The robust cybersecurity practices and privacy-preserving mechanisms should be explored further for GITL. Moreover, ensuring transparency and explainability is crucial; the GAI agent should log interpretable reasoning traces for audit and human verification.

E. Resource constraints and optimization

The integration of GAI in networked robotics inevitably increases computational and communication demands. Future research should investigate resource-aware design principles that jointly optimize energy, computation, and bandwidth usage. Potential strategies include adaptive model compression, hierarchical inference between edge and cloud resources, and dynamic task scheduling based on real-time resource availability. Such mechanisms are essential to ensure scalable, efficient, and sustainable operation of GITL-enabled robotic systems.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This article presented GITL as a comprehensive framework for enhancing the coordination and autonomy of networked robotics in future 6G scenarios. By harnessing GAI models, particularly LLMs, across communication, robot control, and AI model lifecycle loops, our approach demonstrates how integrated semantic reasoning can reduce overhead, adapt

to evolving demands, and enable real-time decision making. This method transcends traditional communication–control co-design by leveraging GAI for multi-layer optimization. Moving forward, practical deployment of GITL requires addressing inference latency, trustworthiness, and standardization challenges across diverse platforms. Concurrent advances in AI model development and distributed computing will be vital to ensure robust, secure, and efficient operations. We believe that GITL marks a pivotal milestone toward autonomous, intelligent, and collaborative robotics, ultimately shaping the 6G robotics landscape.

REFERENCES

- [1] P. Li and A. Aijaz, “Task-Oriented Connectivity for Networked Robotics with Generative AI and Semantic Communications,” in *IEEE INFOCOM 2025 - IEEE Conference on Computer Communications Workshops (INFOCOM WKSHPS)*, 2025, pp. 1–6.
- [2] I. F. Priyanta *et al.*, “Towards 6G-driven cooperative robot framework for unified sensing in smart warehouses,” in *Proc. of IEEE CSCN*. IEEE, 2024, pp. 389–395.
- [3] M. Ghassemian *et al.*, “Standardisation landscape for 6G robotic services,” in *Proc. of IEEE CSCN*. IEEE, 2023, pp. 148–154.
- [4] P. Li, Z. An, S. Abrar, and L. Zhou, “Large language models for multi-robot systems: A survey,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:2502.03814*, 2025.
- [5] A. Lykov *et al.*, “Industry 6.0: New generation of industry driven by generative ai and swarm of heterogeneous robots,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:2409.10106*, 2024.
- [6] H. Zhang, A. B. Sediq, A. Afana, and M. Erol-Kantarci, “Generative AI-in-the-loop: Integrating LLMs and GPTs into the Next Generation Networks,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:2406.04276*, 2024.
- [7] A. Aijaz, “Infrastructure-less wireless connectivity for mobile robotic systems in logistics: Why bluetooth mesh networking is important?” in *Proc. of 26th IEEE ETFA*. IEEE, 2021, pp. 1–8.
- [8] X. An *et al.*, “Multi-robot systems and cooperative object transport: Communications, platforms, and challenges,” *IEEE Open Journal of the Computer Society*, vol. 4, pp. 23–36, 2023.
- [9] M. Dorigo, M. Birattari, and M. Brambilla, “Swarm robotics,” *Scholarpedia*, vol. 9, no. 1, p. 1463, 2014.
- [10] D. Yu, J. Li, Z. Wang, and X. Li, “An Overview of Swarm Coordinated Control,” *IEEE Transactions on Artificial Intelligence*, vol. 5, no. 5, pp. 1918–1938, 2024.
- [11] S.-J. Chung *et al.*, “A Survey on Aerial Swarm Robotics,” *IEEE Transactions on Robotics*, vol. 34, no. 4, pp. 837–855, 2018.
- [12] D. Milutinović and P. Lima, “Modeling and Optimal Centralized Control of a Large-Size Robotic Population,” *IEEE Transactions on Robotics*, vol. 22, no. 6, pp. 1280–1285, 2006.
- [13] R. Simmons, “Structured control for autonomous robots,” *IEEE Transactions on Robotics and Automation*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 34–43, 1994.
- [14] A. Giusti and M. Althoff, “Automatic centralized controller design for modular and reconfigurable robot manipulators,” in *Proc. of IEEE/RSJ IROS*, 2015, pp. 3268–3275.
- [15] P. Li, I. Mavromatis, T. Farnham, A. Aijaz, and A. Khan, “Adapting MLOps for Diverse In-Network Intelligence in 6G Era: Challenges and Solutions,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:2410.18793*, 2024.